

PAPER TITLE

“Transonic Compressor Linear Cascade with an Oscillating Single Blade”.

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OBJECTIVES

Experimental Aeroelasticity, Unsteady Aerodynamics,
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SUMMARY

A lack of experimental data on flutter phenomena in transonic turbomachines hamper further improvements of computational design prediction in particular for off-design operation regimes. A new dedicated test facility has been built at the Institute of Thermomechanics of the Czech Academy of Sciences (IT CAS) to broaden an experimental data base on this topic. The test facility is a five-blade transonic linear cascade provided with a driver to forcedly oscillate the cascade middle blade. Experimental data were collected over a wide range of blade oscillation frequencies up to 210 Hz, blade oscillation amplitude of 1 deg, and for the inlet Mach numbers ranging from 0.5 up to 1.1. Only the results for subsonic inlet Mach numbers of 0.5, 0.7 and 0.9 are discussed in this paper. The range of investigated reduced frequencies for a blade chord of 120 mm and for the test conditions presented here is up to a value of 0.46. The newly acquired experimental data was used to analyze effects of basic parameters on amplitude of induced pressure fluctuations. It appears that the cascade inlet Mach number plays a role as an independent parameter.

BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION

The problem of flutter predictions and blade fatigue failures has not yet been systematically resolved in particular for off-design regimes of turbomachines in spite of significant advancements in structural and aerodynamic computational methods achieved in the last decades. The major reason for slow progress in this area is an overall lack of reliable experimental data that can serve as a base for theoretical build-ups. In particular, it is absolutely true for the high transonic flutter data

A basic equation describing induced oscillatory motion of a turbomachine blade caused by aeroelastic effects consists of two main components: the structural side and the aerodynamic excitation side. The major unknown in this equation is the excitation force / loading function, which is out-of-phase with the blade oscillatory motion. Without sufficient knowledge of the blade loading variation in time it is impossible to affirm if the blade will continue to flutter or not after the initial deflection. It is not always possible to construct new blades to be flutter resistant because the aerodynamic excitation force is not adequately known beforehand during the blade design cycle.

Presently, the aerodynamic excitation force can be determined only by experimental investigations [1-4]. Knowledge of the periodic loading force is needed to determine the work done by the fluid on the blade per an oscillatory cycle. If the aerodynamic work done on the blade by the fluid is positive then the blade will be induced into oscillations. In contrast, if the aerodynamic work is negative, which means that the blade dissipates energy into the fluid, then the oscillating blade will be damped and eventually it will stop oscillating. To determine the loading experimentally is quite a complex and demanding process. At present, the only solution is to rely on experimental data acquired in specialized test facilities trying to approximate, for better or worse, the real turbomachine conditions. Such facilities must generate transonic flow rate, must be provided with high-speed blade oscillatory drivers, and must be equipped with top high-speed instrumentation and data acquisition systems. In short, such facilities are rare and very expensive.

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The goal of the current work is to generate a reliable experimental data base that will be available for general use for verification and refinement of computational prediction

methods. The experimental work was carried out at the High-Speed Laboratory (HSL) of the Institute of Thermomechanics of the Czech Academy of Sciences (IT CAS) in a newly built blade flutter test facility. The basic experimental arrangement is shown in Figure 1. The five-blade linear cascade was modified to provide a driver for the cascade middle blade. The test module, called Blade Flutter Module (BFM) is depicted in Figure 2. A high-speed drive connected to the cascade middle blade is shown in the figure. The test module is inserted into a transonic wind tunnel as presented in Figure 3. A cross section of a transonic compressor test blade [Reference 5] is in Figure 4. The blade instrumentation with miniature high-frequency pressure transducers is also depicted in the figure.

Figure 4. Instrumented test blades.

Experimental data were collected over a wide range of blade oscillation frequencies up to 210 Hz, blade oscillation amplitude of 1 deg, and for the inlet Mach numbers ranging from 0.5 up to 1.1. Only the results for subsonic inlet Mach numbers of 0.5, 0.7 and 0.9 are discussed in this paper. The range of investigated reduced frequencies for a blade chord of 120 mm as well as for the test conditions presented here is up to a value of 0.46.

Samples of recorded pressures are shown in Figure 5. The presented data is for the inlet Mach number of 0.9. The snippets are 200 ms long cut-outs from the overall 4-second records. Presented data are from the first tap on the suction surface of the active middle blade (BL3, $x/c = 0.193$). Diagrams reveal the effects of gradually increasing forced blade oscillation frequency on evolution of surface pressure fluctuations. It should be noted that the blade oscillation amplitude also increases with the increasing frequency, though the blade driver operates at a constant amplitude of 1 deg. Due to acceleration forces the blade front part flexes, which increases the actual incidence angle offset. The reported values of blade amplitudes were measured at a blade tip ($x/c = 0.040$) by a laser displacement sensor with a resolution of 0.05 deg.

The individual pressure signals, blade angular position, and driver rotation were sampled simultaneously with sampling frequency of 40 kHz. Recorded driver oscillatory data were used as a time base for ensemble averaging of all other time signals. The ensemble averaged data are presented on a dimensionless basis of a single oscillation period. A typical record of an ensemble-averaged pressure oscillations during the blade oscillation cycle is presented in Figure 6.

OVERVIEW OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The reported unsteady pressure data were recorded on the suction surface of the cascade middle blade (blade BL3). Data were recorded at seven positions along the blade chord. Data for only four pressure taps located at chord fractions of 0.193, 0.400, 0.646 and 0.883 are reported here. The presented results are for cascade three subsonic inlet flow numbers of Mach numbers of 0.5, 0.7 and 0.9.

Figure 1. Arrangement of flutter test cascade.

Figure 2. Mechanism of blade flutter test module.

Figure 3. IT CAS transonic wind tunnel.

Figure 5. Segments of recorded pressure at various blade oscillation frequencies.

Figure 6. Ensemble averaged period of pressure fluctuations and blade periodic motion.

The summary plot in Figure 7 depicts four pressure distributions and a distribution of the blade tip angular position during one ensemble average period of the blade oscillation. The blade oscillation frequency is 100 Hz and the cascade inlet Mach number is 0.7. A corresponding value of the reduced frequency based on the blade full chord is 0.158. The blade tip motion is denoted by the dashed curve. As seen here, the blade oscillatory motion is nearly a perfect sine wave. The four other solid color curves represent the recorded pressure fluctuation waves. The shape of the pressure data wave at $x/c = 0.193$ (the green curve) is also very close to a sine wave albeit with a phase delay of 180 deg with respect to the blade motion wave. The remaining pressure distributions for taps further from the blade leading edge show increasing phase delay with respect to the blade motion wave. A velocity of the pressure front wave with respect to the flow velocity and along the blade chord location can be determined from these data.

Figure 7. Pressure waves at four chord locations measured at $Ma_1 = 0.7$ and $f_b = 100$ Hz

Figure 8. Pressure waves at four chord locations measured at $Ma_1 = 0.5$ and $f_b = 200$ Hz.

Figure 9. Pressure waves at four chord locations measured at $Ma_1 = 0.7$ and $f_b = 200$ Hz

Figure 10. Pressure waves at four chord locations measured at $Ma_1 = 0.9$ and $f_b = 200$ Hz

The same picture format was used for the following Figures 8 through 10. The cascade inlet Mach number was gradually set to 0.5, 0.7 and 0.9 level as marked in the figures. The blade oscillation frequency was kept constant at a level of 200 Hz for all three cases. The shape of pressure distribution waves within the oscillation period for the two lower inlet Mach numbers of 0.5 and 0.7 resembles the distributions already shown in Figure 7. Amplitudes of pressure oscillations are larger due to a larger amplitude of the blade angular oscillations caused by the blade tip flexing. As mentioned before the blade flexing increases the effective blade amplitude to 1.1 deg at a frequency of 100 Hz and even more to a value of 2.0 deg at a frequency of 200 Hz, whereas the drive mechanism amplitude is always kept constant at 1.0 deg. It appears that increasing the oscillation frequency also the phase delays among the pressure measurement stations along the blade chord is increased. It should be noted, for the highest inlet Mach number of 0.9, shown in Figure 10, there is a detectable deformation of the pressure distribution acquired at the first pressure tap at a relative chord of 0.193. Data recorded at the remaining pressure taps, more distant from the blade leading edge, seem to mimic the previously measured data at lower inlet Mach numbers. The shown pressure distribution acquired at $x/c = 0.193$ deviates from a pure sine wave shape, spotting a large hump around a mid of the oscillation period.

The noticed inconsistency in the pressure fluctuations in the blade zone close to the leading edge is revealed with better clarity in Figure 11. Data measured at the $x/c = 0.193$ are mutually compared for three inlet Mach numbers upstream of the test cascade. As seen here, there is a nearly perfect sine wave shape of the pressure waves for the two low inlet Mach numbers of 0.5 and 0.7. Results of similar measurements taken at a chord fraction of $x/c = 0.400$ are presented in Figure 12. The shape of amplitudes of pressure waves at this chord location is again very close to a perfect sine wave. The diagram indicates that at this chord location the inlet flow subsonic Mach number affects only the pressure wave amplitude. The phase of the pressure waves is not affected at all.

It appears that the pressure wave anomaly observed in Figures 10 and 11 is limited only to the blade surface zone close to the blade tip and to the inlet flows nearing the transonic velocity range. As seen in the lowest diagram in Figure 5, there are occasional downward spikes indicating random instances when the local flow velocity reaches the sonic level. An enlarged view of one of the downward spikes in Figure 13. Such dropdowns were observed at irregular intervals seemingly not affected or synchronized with the blade oscillation frequency. The downward spikes appear only at the highest oscillation frequency, probably induced by momentary unsteadiness bursts at the blade leading edge or upstream of the cascade not related to nevertheless reinforced by the blade oscillation frequency. The observed asynchronous events resemble transonic intermittency reported in Reference 7. Consequently a question arises about a data reduction and the

Figure 11. Pressure waves measured at $x/c = 0.193$ and blade frequency of 200 Hz for three inlet Mach numbers.

Figure 12. Pressure waves measured at $x/c = 0.400$ and blade frequency of 200 Hz for three inlet Mach numbers.

Figure 13. Segment of pressure data with an occasional pressure drop (velocity burst) approaching sonic conditions.

presentation methodology for flow conditions with a certain level of aperiodicity. In particular the question is about the rightness of ensemble averaging the entire data record. Would it be rather more proper to allocate subsonic and transonic wavelets into separate groups, then perform ensemble averages independently, and determine the final outcome by proportional contribution of both groups.

MACH NUMBER EFFECTS

The wide base of acquired experimental data was used to analyze effects of basic parameters on amplitude of induced pressure fluctuations. Amplitudes of pressure fluctuations were determined as a half of the peak-to-peak pressure difference in the particular ensemble average data (e.g. Figure 6). A summary graph of pressure absolute amplitudes as a function of the blade reduced frequency is shown in Figure 14 (note that the reduce frequency is based on the full blade chord). It is clear in this plot that the cascade inlet Mach number plays a role as an independent parameter. As stated before, due to the blade edge bending the angular amplitude of an oscillating blade depends on the oscillation frequency as shown in Figure 15. Consequently, the variability of the blade angular amplitude must be accounted for. Therefore, a relative amplitude, which is a ratio of a pressure amplitude and a corresponding blade angular amplitude, was plotted to eliminate the bias induced by the dependence of the blade angular amplitude on oscillation frequency. The resulting graph is in Figure 16. As seen here, the effects of the inlet Mach number on relative pressure amplitudes are still strong. Finally, the blade relative amplitudes were normalized by the particular dynamic pressure and replotted again as a function of the blade reduced frequency. A graph with normalized pressure oscillation amplitudes is presented in Figure 17. Obviously, the normalization by the inlet dynamic pressure noticeably suppressed the effects of the inlet Mach number on the spread of pressure amplitude data. Albeit, some residual data scatter can still be noted. An additional data analysis is still needed, in particular for data acquired from surface pressure taps further downstream of the blade leading edge.

MEASUREMENT ACCURACY

The utmost care was paid to the accuracy of the acquired data. All steady pressure data were measured by a scanner with a pressure transducer with a rated full-scale accuracy of 0.05 % and a resolution better the 50 Pa. Unsteady pressure data were measured by miniature pressure transducers of a full-scale of 100 kPa. Each of the miniature transducers was individual calibrated in a range of vacuum pressures between 20 kPa and 100 kPa. The accuracy of all transducers was 1% at full scale or better. Blade incidence angle offset for static test runs was measured with a digital angle finder of a resolution of 0.1 deg. An amplitude of the oscillating blade was measured with a laser displacement sensor with a resolution of 0.05 deg.

Figure 14. Effects of cascade inlet Mach number on absolute amplitude of pressure oscillations.

Figure 15. Dependence of blade angular amplitude on driver frequency.

Figure 16. Effects of cascade inlet Mach number on ratio of pressure and blade amplitudes.

Figure 17. Effects of cascade inlet Mach number on relative amplitude of pressure oscillations normalized by cascade inlet dynamic pressure.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

The work aimed at producing a reliable experimental data base to be available for general use for verification and refinement of computational code dealing with flutter phenomena in turbomachines. The necessary prerequisite was attesting an operation reliability of a newly designed and built test facility for transonic flutter research. Blade Flutter Module proved to be fully operational and is available for an advanced blade flutter research. A random appearance of pressure drops to sonic conditions at a high subsonic inlet flow has been demonstrated. An intermittency of pressure drops below the level of induced pressure fluctuations might contribute to non-synchronized blade vibrations.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS

BFM	... Blade Flutter Module
BL#	... blade location in cascade
CAS	... Czech Academy of Sciences
HSL	... High Speed Laboratory
IT	... Institute of Thermomechanics

A_p	... pressure amplitude
c	... blade chord length
f_b	... blade oscillation frequency
k	... reduced frequency (full chord)
Ma_1	... inlet Mach number
$p(t)$... surface local pressure
t	... time
x	... horizontal direction
α	... blade amplitude
τ	... oscillation period fraction

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